

Developing IN-CORE Community App: Web Application for Community Resilience

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Abstract— Community resilience assessment is critical for the anticipation, prevention and mitigation of natural and anthropic disaster impacts. In the digital age, this requires reliable and flexible cyberinfrastructure capable of supporting research and decision processes along multiple simultaneous, interconnected concerns. To address this need, the National Center for Supercomputing Applications (NCSA) developed the Interdependent Networked Community Resilience Modeling Environment (IN-CORE) as part of the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST)-funded Center of Excellence for Risk-Based Community Resilience Planning (CoE), headquartered at Colorado State University. The Community App is a web-based application that takes a community through the resilience planning process using IN-CORE analyses for the measurement science to measure community resilience. Complex workflows are managed by DataWolf, a scientific workflow management system, running jobs on the IN-CORE platform utilizing the underlying Kubernetes cluster resources. Using the community app, users can perform realistic and complex scenarios and visualize the results to understand their resilience to different hazards and enhance their decision-making capabilities.

Keywords—Community Resilience, Computing Platform, Hazard Risk Assessment, Scientific Workflow System, Container Technology, Kubernetes

I. INTRODUCTION

To date, three IN-CORE community apps [1] have been developed for the cities of Joplin, MO, Salt Lake City, UT, and Galveston, TX that demonstrate how community apps for different hazards and infrastructures can be developed for communities using IN-CORE based on their risk. For example, Joplin had the costliest and deadliest single tornado in the USA in the last half century in 2011 and is at high risk to tornado events. Each community app uses IN-CORE [2] analyses for the measurement science to measure community resilience to different hazards and to help users make informed decisions. The Joplin app looks at resilience to Tornado Hazards; Salt Lake

City looks at earthquake and liquefaction hazards, and Galveston looks at hurricane hazards. The community app consists of 3 primary components. The frontend is written in ReactJS and uses a modular framework so each community app can be tailored to the specific community characteristics and hazards. It uses a Restful web service developed by Python FastAPI called the Maestro service for storing step state and other app information that needs to be persisted by the web application. Finally, the frontend is built around a complex scientific workflow consisting of pyIncore analyses and other post-processing tools that are setup and executed by the frontend using an open source scientific workflow system called DataWolf [3]. Results of workflow executions are then visualized in the web application to help users make informed decisions.

II. COMMUNITY APP AS WEB APPLICATION

The User Interface of the community app is designed by adopting A Playbook: NIST Community Resilience Planning guide to help communities with resilience planning. IN-CORE analyses and capabilities are inserted into the playbook guide as shown in Fig 1.

Fig. 1. Integrating the NIST Playbook and IN-CORE

The results of the measurement science brings better understanding of their resilience to different hazard events and

the impacts they might have on their community. The ReactJS application consists of two parts - the core contains common web components required for all community apps and then a specific implementation that builds against the core and includes community specific widgets for the hazard, the workflow behind the community app and any specific visualizations for outputs. Each app is configurable to support community specific hazard type, infrastructure types, and map visualizations. The community app steps the user through different parts of the playbook of planning guide and allows users to define the hazard for the community, upload the built environment components such as buildings, electric power, fragilities, and run different scenarios using these data. Users can select the inputs they want to run for a specific scenario and then submit these to DataWolf to execute the workflow. Once the job is finished, users can use the community app to explore results such as anticipated economic impact, population dislocation, housing recovery, etc. to inform community planning. Fig 2 shows an example of the Galveston island dislocation and building damage for the 1% annual probability of exceedance (AEP) scenario. Planners can use this information to inform building codes and other planning.

Fig. 2. Population dislocation Result for City of Galveston, TX.

III. MAESTRO SERVICE

The community app is designed to be a collaborative tool used by a planning team with different roles and tasks. To facilitate this, the community app uses the Maestro service to handle setting up the team, assigning roles, storing the status of each playbook step, links to any collaborative documents, and other information that needs to be persisted for the web application. It uses PostgreSQL Database and CRUD models for persisting changes in playbook steps and managing user roles since each community app will be community specific with assigned community leaders responsible for different tasks. Playbook tasks/steps can be assigned to different team members and those who are part of the team can see each other's outputs so they can work collaboratively on resilience planning.

IV. KUBERNETES EXECUTOR FOR DATAWOLF

The community app is the frontend to a complex, multi-step workflow that consists of tools the wrap pyIncore scientific analyses and other post processing tools to determine the

anticipated performance of the community under different scenarios. DataWolf [4] has a REST API that allows an external application to run a workflow as a service and retrieve the outputs from an execution. As part of the development of the community app, a Kubernetes executor was developed that allows DataWolf to create and run workflow tools as Kubernetes jobs if DataWolf is running on a Kubernetes cluster. This greatly improved the load balancing of jobs since analyses that require large memory or computing resources can be created as Kubernetes tools and utilize resources available on the cluster while less compute and memory intensive tools can be executed locally on DataWolf. This allowed for much better scaling and performance of the workflows since tools with large resource requirements could be offloaded to the cluster. Each Kubernetes workflow tool mounts a volume for storing any output files generated by the tool so they can be stored in DataWolf before the pod is terminated. For managing Kubernetes jobs, DataWolf uses the Kubernetes Java Client to communicate with the cluster. The Java client allows DataWolf to submit jobs to the cluster, check status and terminate jobs. The community app can check DataWolf for job status and as steps are finished, data can be retrieved through DataWolf's REST API or the IN-CORE service REST API for visualizing the results.

V. CONCLUSION

Many communities have a very good understanding of what natural hazard(s) they are susceptible to; however, what is missing in many cases is a comprehensive understanding of what their resilience is to a specific hazard and how to use that information to inform community planning. The community app can help communities to understand their resilience to different hazards by providing the measurement science to better inform community planning and improve resilience. In addition, as the IN-CORE platform [5] is developed and released with new and improved science and data, these updates are available to new and existing community apps so they are using the latest science and engineering to inform community planning

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